

Publication and Maintenance of Relational Data in Enterprise Knowledge Graphs

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Abstract. Enterprise knowledge graphs (EKG) is a novel paradigm used to consolidate and semantically integrate large numbers of heterogeneous data sources into a comprehensive dataspace. The main goal of an EKG is to provide a data layer, which is semantically connected to enterprise data, so that applications can have integrated access to enterprise data sources through that semantic layer. To make legacy relational data sources accessible through the organization's knowledge graph, it is necessary to create an RDF view of the underlying relational data (RDB2RDF view). An RDB2RDF view can be materialized to improve query performance and data availability. However, a materialized RDB2RDF view must be continuously maintained to reflect updates over the relational database. The authors proposed a formal framework for the construction of the materialized data graph for an RDB2RDF view, and for incremental maintenance of the view's data graph. Also presents an architecture and algorithms to implement the proposed framework and described experiments that confirm the validity and value of the proposed approach. This paper shows the theorems and their proofs for the proposed approach.

Definition 1. Let Ψ be a TR in M and r_1, \dots, r_n be tuple variables appearing in Ψ associated with relations R_1, \dots, R_n , where $n \geq 2$ and $r_i \neq r_j$ for $i \neq j$. Also, let σ be a database state and let p_1, \dots, p_n be tuples in $R_1(\sigma), \dots, R_n(\sigma)$.

1. $\Psi[r_1/p_1, \dots, r_n/p_n]$ denotes the Transformation Rule (TR) obtained from Ψ by substituting the tuples p_1, \dots, p_n for the tuple variables r_1, \dots, r_n , respectively.
2. $\Psi[r_1/p_1, \dots, r_n/p_n](\sigma)$ denotes the set of triples which are produced when $\Psi[r_1/p_1, \dots, r_n/p_n]$ is applied to σ .

Definition 2 (RDF state of a tuple). Let σ be a database state and let R be a pivot relation in M . The RDF state of tuple p in $R(\sigma)$, denoted $M[p](\sigma)$, is defined as:

$$M[p](\sigma) = \{(s, q, o, g) \mid (s, q, o) \text{ is a triple in } \Psi[r/p](\sigma) \text{ where } \Psi \text{ is a TR in } M \text{ with pivot relation } R, \text{ and } g \text{ is the named graph URI for pivot relation } R\}.$$

Definition 3 (RDF state of a relation). Let σ be a database state of \mathbf{S} and R be a relation in \mathbf{S} . The RDF state of R at state σ , denoted $M[R](\sigma)$, is defined as:

$$M[R](\sigma) = \bigcup_{p \text{ is a tuple in } R(\sigma)} M[p](\sigma)$$

Definition 4 (Materialization of \mathcal{W}). The materialization or state of \mathcal{W} at state σ , denoted $M(\sigma)$, is defined as:

$$M(\sigma) = \bigcup_{\substack{p \text{ is a tuple in } R(\sigma) \text{ and} \\ R \text{ is a Pivot Relation of } \mathcal{W}}} M[p](\sigma)$$

Definition 5 (updates, insertions and deletions). An update on a relation R is a pair $u=(D, I)$ such that D and I are, possibly empty, sets of tuples of R . If $I = \emptyset$, the authors say that the update is a deletion, and, if $D=\emptyset$, they say that the update is an insertion.

The semantics of an update $u = (D, I)$ is straightforward and is defined as follows:

Definition 6 (semantics of an update). Let $u = (D, I)$ be an update on R and σ_0 be a database state. Then, the execution of u on σ_0 results in the database state σ_1 which is equal to σ_0 except that $R(\sigma_1) = R(\sigma_0) - D \cup I$. The authors also say that σ_1 is the result of executing u on σ_0 and that σ_0 is the database state before u and σ_1 is the database state after u .

Definition 7. Let R be a relation in \mathbf{S} .

1. Let Ψ be a TR in M . R is relevant to Ψ iff R appears in the body of Ψ or R is referenced by a foreign key in the body of Ψ .
2. R is relevant to view \mathcal{W} iff R is relevant to some TR in M .
3. Let u be an update on relation R . A relation R^* in \mathbf{S} is relevant to u iff R^* is the pivot relation of a TR Ψ in M and R is relevant to Ψ .

Lemma 1. Let u be an update on a relation R , and let σ_0 and σ_1 be the database states before and after u , respectively.

1. If R is not relevant to \mathcal{W} , then $M(\sigma_0) = M(\sigma_1)$. Thus, an update on a relation that is not relevant to the view does not affect the state of the view.
2. Let R^* be a relation in \mathbf{S} . If R^* is not relevant to u , then $M[R^*](\sigma_0) = M[R^*](\sigma_1)$. Thus, an update u does not affect the RDF state of the relations which are not relevant to u .

Proof.

1. From Definition 7.2, if R is not relevant to \mathcal{W} then R does not appear in the body of any rule in M and R is not referenced by a foreign key in the body of any such rule. From Definitions 1 and 2, this means that the RDF state of any tuple in a pivot relation R^* is independent of the tuples in the state of R . So, updates on R do not affect the RDF state of any pivot relation of \mathcal{W} . Thus, from Definition 3, updates on R do not affect the state of view \mathcal{W} .
2. From Definition 7.3, if R^* is not relevant to u , then the updated relation R is not relevant to any TR Ψ , where R^* is the pivot relation. Thus, R does not appear in the body of any rule that has R^* as pivot relation and R is not referenced by a foreign key in the body of any such rule. But this means that the RDF state of any tuple in R^* is independent of the tuples in the state of R . Since only the state of R can change from σ_0 to σ_1 , it follows that $M[R^*](\sigma_0) = M[R^*](\sigma_1)$.

Definition 8. Let:

- $u=(D, I)$ be an update on R .
- σ_0 and σ_1 be the database states before and after u , respectively.
- Ψ be a TR in M , where R is relevant to Ψ , r is the pivot relation of Ψ , r and r^* are the tuple variables for R and R^* in Ψ , respectively.

1. Let r_{old} be a tuple in D .
 $\mathcal{P}[R, \Psi](r_{old}) = \{p \mid p \text{ is a tuple in } R^*(\sigma_0) \text{ and } (\Psi[r^*/p, r/t](\sigma_0) \neq \emptyset)\}$.
2. Let r_{new} be a tuple in I .
 $\mathcal{P}[R, \Psi](r_{new}) = \{p \mid p \text{ is a tuple in } R^*(\sigma_1) \text{ and } (\Psi[r^*/p, r/t](\sigma_1) \neq \emptyset)\}$.
3. A tuple p in $R^*(\sigma_0) \cup R^*(\sigma_1)$ is relevant to u w.r.t. Ψ iff p is in $\mathcal{P}[R, \Psi](t)$ for some t in $D \cup I$.

Definition 9. Let $u=(D, I)$ be an update on R and σ_0 and σ_1 be the database states before and after u , respectively. A tuple p in $\sigma_0 \cup \sigma_1$ is relevant to u iff:

1. p is relevant to u w.r.t. a TR Ψ in M , or
2. p occurs in $D \cup I$ and R is a pivot relation of a TR in M .

Lemma 2. Let $u=(D, I)$ be an update on R . Let R^* be a relation relevant to u and let p be a tuple in $R^*(\sigma_0)$, but not in D . If p is not relevant to u w.r.t. any TR Ψ in M then $M[p](\sigma_0) = M[p](\sigma_1)$.

Proof. Let $u=(D, I)$ be an update on R . Let R^* be a relation relevant to u and let p be a tuple in $R^*(\sigma_0)$, but not in D . Suppose p is not relevant to u w.r.t. any TR in M . Define:

$$T_0 = \bigcup_{\substack{R^* \text{ is relevant} \\ \text{to } \Psi \text{ and } t \in D}} \Psi[r^*/p, r/t](\sigma_0) \text{ and } T_1 = \bigcup_{\substack{R^* \text{ is relevant} \\ \text{to } \Psi \text{ and } t \in I}} \Psi[r^*/p, r/t](\sigma_1) \quad (1)$$

Let g be the named graph URI for pivot relation R . Define:

$$Q_0 = \{(s, q, o, g) \mid (s, q, o) \in T_0\} \text{ and } Q_1 = \{(s, q, o, g) \mid (s, q, o) \in T_1\} \quad (2)$$

From Definition 2, and since $R(\sigma_1) = (R(\sigma_0) - D) \cup I$ and $R'(\sigma_1) = R'(\sigma_0)$, for any relation R' distinct from R , we have:

$$M[p](\sigma_1) = (M[p](\sigma_0) - Q_0) \cup Q_1 \quad (3)$$

Since p is not relevant to u , for any transformation rule in M , and since p does not occur in D , from Definition 8, we have:

$$Q_1 = Q_0 = \emptyset. \quad (4)$$

Therefore, we have:

$$M[p](\sigma_1) = M[p](\sigma_0) \quad (5)$$

as desired.

Definition 10 (Changeset for update u). Let $u=(D, I)$ be an update on R . Let \mathcal{P}_0 be the set of tuples in σ_0 that are relevant to u (Definition 9). Let \mathcal{P}_1 be the set of tuples in σ_1 that are relevant to u (Definition 9). Then,

$$\begin{aligned} - \Delta^-(u) &= \bigcup_{p \in \mathcal{P}_0} M[p](\sigma_0) \\ - \Delta^+(u) &= \bigcup_{p \in \mathcal{P}_1} M[p](\sigma_1) \end{aligned}$$

A third auxiliary lemma is needed to prove the central result of the article, which is shown as follows.

Lemma 3. Let σ be database state and, for $i=1,2$, let \mathbf{T}_i be sets of tuples in pivot relations of an RDB2RDF view. Define $Q_i = \{x / x \text{ is a quad in } M[p](\sigma), \text{ where } p \text{ is a tuple in } \mathbf{T}_i\}$. If \mathbf{T}_1 and \mathbf{T}_2 are disjoint, then Q_1 and Q_2 are also disjoint.

Proof.

1. We first prove that transformation rules with the same pivot relation, applied to different pivot tuples, are disjoint. Since the transformation rules are object preserving, different pivot tuples generate triples with different subject. So, different pivot tuples in the same pivot relation do not generate duplicated triple. Therefore, the set of triples generated by transformation rules with the same pivot relation, applied to different pivot tuples, are disjoint and so are their quads.
2. Now, transformation rules with different pivot relations may generate duplicated triples when applied to different pivot tuples (if they use the same hasURI function). However, triples generated by different pivot relations are stored in different named graphs. So, if duplicated triples are produced, they will be in different named graphs. Therefore, the set of quads generated by applying transformation rules, with different pivot relation, for different pivot tuple, are disjoint.

Theorem 1. *Let:*

- $u=(D, I)$ be an update on R
- σ_0 and σ_1 be the database states before and after u
- $\mathcal{P}_0, \mathcal{P}_1, \Delta^-(u)$ and $\Delta^+(u)$ be as in Definition 10

$$\text{Then, } M(\sigma_1) = (M(\sigma_0) - \Delta^-(u)) \cup \Delta^+(u)$$

Proof.

Let

- \mathcal{P}^* be the set of tuples that are not relevant to u .
- $T_0 = \bigcup_{r^* \in \mathcal{P}^*} M[r^*](\sigma_0)$
- $T_1 = \bigcup_{r^* \in \mathcal{P}^*} M[r^*](\sigma_1)$

where T_0 and T_1 contain the old and new states of the tuples that are not relevant to u , respectively. Since the tuples in \mathcal{P}^* are not relevant to u , from Lemma 2, we have that $T_0 = T_1$.

From Definition 4, we have:

$$M(\sigma_0) = \bigcup_{r^* \in B_0} M[r^*](\sigma_0) \text{ where } B_0 = \bigcup_{\substack{R^* \text{ is a} \\ \text{pivot relation}}} R^*(\sigma_0) \quad (1)$$

and

$$M(\sigma_1) = \bigcup_{r^* \in B_1} M[r^*](\sigma_1) \text{ where } B_1 = \bigcup_{\substack{R^* \text{ is a} \\ \text{pivot relation}}} R^*(\sigma_1) \quad (2)$$

Since the only changes from σ_0 to σ_1 is the deletion of tuples in D and the insertion of tuples in I into R , it follows that

$$B_0 = \mathcal{P}^* \cup \mathcal{P}_0 \text{ and } B_1 = \mathcal{P}^* \cup \mathcal{P}_1 \quad (3)$$

From Eqs. (1), (2), and (3) and

$$M(\sigma_0) = T_0 \cup \Delta^-(u) \quad (4)$$

$$M(\sigma_1) = T_1 \cup \Delta^+(u) \quad (5)$$

From Lemma 3, we have that T_0 and $\Delta^-(u)$ are disjoint. Then, from Eq. (4), we have:

$$T_0 = M(\sigma_0) - \Delta^-(u) \quad (6)$$

Recall that $T_0 = T_1$. From Eqs. (5) and (6), we then have

$$M(\sigma_1) = (M(\sigma_0) - \Delta^-(u)) \cup \Delta^+(u)$$

as desired.